

THE ROLE OF LITERATURE IN DEVELOPING HUMAN PERSONALITY

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Abstract: *This article mainly points out the effect of literature in a formation of people's personalities and how it helps them to understand their emotions more accurately. While reading, people might compare themselves with the characters, experience huge amount of emotions, explore new cultures and their core values. In this process, they also will be able to find out about their own inner values, evaluate the consequences of their decisions, and would have time to understand their emotions and true self. Using the book of Laurent Gounelle “The God Always Travels Incognito” as a personal example, the article focuses on emphasizing the power of literature in developing one's personality in action. Ultimately, literature serves as a personal guide, therapist and a true friend, helping people to develop their critical thinking, creativity and most importantly, helps them to shape their personality.*

Key words: *literature, feelings, emotions, teenagers, people, readers.*

Introduction. For as long as people have existed, literature has been one of the most powerful tools that helped them to develop their personality, the way they saw the life and helped them to distinguish the good and the evil. It has always been there for us, both now and then. It does not only make us forget harsh reality, but also, it teaches, questions, and changes us. Through reading, we get an opportunity to feel wide range of emotions, experience the diverse cultures, that help us understand the world around us. Scholars emphasize that engagement with literary texts allows readers to explore multiple perspectives and gradually construct their personal identity through narrative experience.¹ Empirical research suggests that reading literary fiction can enhance readers' empathy and theory of mind by promoting sensitivity to others' mental states². In this way, literature plays a huge role in building a person's identity and inner self. I felt this myself while reading “The God Always Travels Incognito” by Laurent Gounelle. This novel deeply touched me and made me think of the things I do naturally without thinking that shows people who am I, and even how it might give a wrong impression of me to them without my will. I felt so alike to the main hero, and with the help of this book I got to change the parts of myself that I didn't liked much. So, again, it made me realize, how reading can be powerful enough to help someone discover themselves and make changes for the better.

Main part. Many people question, why we talk about literature so much, how can we possibly benefit from such a simple thing as reading? Well, let me give answers to these questions then. Literature is the ultimately the greatest time saver! Although, people see it as a time wasting, and some would probably prioritize doing other more “meaningful things”, like house chores, literature actually saves us the huge amount of time that nobody could have think of. Since, it takes

¹ Appleyard, J. A. (1990). *Becoming a reader: The experience of fiction from childhood to adulthood*. Cambridge University Press.

² Kidd, D. C., & Castano, E. (2013). Reading literary fiction improves theory of mind. *Science*, 342(6156), 377–380. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1239918>

us among a several range of emotions and events that would take to learn for decades and even centuries to experience them directly. Literature puts us through far more situations that we could ever directly witness. It let's us to see what it's like to get divorced, kill someone and feel remorseful about it, or from being a billionaire going down to being completely broke, or make a terrible mistake when everyone was believing in your success and to the other countless experiences you might never get through in your life by just living it. Literature takes us through different dimensions, continents and centuries, while doing so curing our provincialism, by reminding us there is a world that is diverse, far beyond the environment in which we are living. Additionally, literature shows us how things looks like from someone else's point of view, it makes us think about the consequences of our actions on others in a way we could not have think of. It shows us examples of kindly, generous, sympathetic people, highlighting that it is not so hard to be a good person while living in bad conditions. Honestly, almost everybody struggles with saying out loud what is on their minds, as some find it embarrassing, some think it is weird and others simply do not want to open up. But in books, we find the descriptions of who we genuinely are, the characters we believe that are strangely alike to us. We relate to them, try to predict their next move, they will probably take the path that we would take, because we see the world in an almost the same way as they do. In the best books you can read it feels like writer knows us better than we know ourselves, like that person wants to show us how they understand us. Because the being understood without judgements is one of the best moments of life that any human being can experience. And another thing worth mentioning about literature is that it prepares us to the failure. All of our lives, one of our greatest fears is of falling, of messing up, and of becoming a loser that everyone would avoid. Interestingly, a lot of literature is also about failure. Hynes and Hynes-Berry suggest that literary narratives can provide readers with non-judgmental spaces for reflecting on failure, thereby supporting emotional insight and self-acceptance.³

Many famous poems, novels are about people who have made small or a huge mistake, but great books don't judge as harshly as society would. They evoke pity for the hero and make us think of how we could be hard on ourselves, sometimes. It teaches us how to be gentle on ourselves, how the world will not come to an end if we keep making mistakes, and that is the beauty of reading. Not a waste of time, not a second priority but the power that could change our lives for good. One of the most profound ways it does so is by teaching us to distinguish what is right and wrong. Through stories, we face with conflicts that are the reflections of the real-life struggles, such as the justice and revenge, courage and fear, a lie for good and an honesty that might harm. Readers can observe the consequences of character's decisions, and get insights for themselves, which is the quiet form of moral education that we might overlook when encountered directly. Since we can not observe and know everything about any person to get an idea for ourselves if they are doing right or wrong, unlike in books where we would know everything about that specific character. And their decisions give us a subconscious morality lesson, which would change the way we think and the way we see the world. Another significant element of literature's way of moral influence is by showing the process of decision making in details. It does not only show the “right vs wrong”, but shows how people might be forced to choose the thing that they never wanted to opt for. This might be out of their fear, confusion or desperation. Not all the wrong choices made by bad people. When readers see all that, they develop more mature understanding of the world, they start to avoid being judgmental, as they don't know the stories of life the people

³ Hynes, A. M., & Hynes-Berry, M. (2011). *Bibliotherapy: The interactive process* (2nd ed.). Libraries Unlimited.

they meet in real life. Literature also helps us question the stereotypes, traditions in our society. Many books illustrate the unfairness towards powerless people from the side of government, or from people with power. When we read such stories, it ignites the feeling of empathy for them and we start to love the characters who fight for justice, which will teach us that speaking up is not bad as it is described by the society. It is about courage to stand up for our morals, even when it is difficult, even when it is not welcomed. This way, literature teaches readers to stand against the things that they are not comfortable with or against the ignorant unfairness. Through emotional stories, it guides us to be more mature, thoughtful, and morally aware individuals.

While, literature guides toward strong sense of right and wrong, it also creates an escape zone for those who are tired of the hustle and bustle of their own life. Readers would be able to transform themselves into any atmosphere they want by choosing the book genre accordingly. Usually, while reading, people unwind, regain emotional balance, and process how they really feel by being in the safe, relaxing atmosphere of literature. They often find reflections of their own problems in books that some characters face, and readers might feel like they are not alone in their struggles which gives them a sense of being emotionally supported. So, literature serves as therapy, from which readers can heal their wounded souls.

It is also significant to point out that, literature is a vital contributor to language-learning students. They might read any piece of literature that is in the language that they are learning, and the consistent reading in that specific language could contribute to the improvement of their skills in the language. Since, it will broaden their linguistic range and allows them to have a vivid picture of how the real speech looks like in that particular language. As readers would encounter the new ways of delivering ideas, it would be easier for them to express their own thoughts, and sometimes they might get a bit more confident as they would now the order of presenting ideas.

From my personal experience, I believe that the literature plays a crucial role in forming the personality of teenagers as they are in the process of growing up. When youngsters face up with new emotions, fears, and more intensified feelings that are not alike with the ones they used to feel, they might get overwhelmed with all of the rage, anxiety, insecurity and other many new things that they have not felt before, they might feel helpless and useless. Obviously, asking for help from adults might be a solution, but most teenagers are too ashamed to pronounce their struggles, that is why literature appears like a saver. What it does, is to show them that there are different people, from different backgrounds, with different problems, who chose different paths but almost with the same destiny. If they were driven by morals and justice there is a good ending waiting for them and the quite opposite for the people who had chosen a path which made people around them suffer. And in the process of reading such stories, they will get to know about the conflicts, fears and doubts of the characters that might feel relatable, which way it will make them to have a clear imagination of what they want to become and how they will overcome the problems that they are facing or might face. Also, they will know about the consequences of their choices, which gives them space to think, analyze and realize their values and true individuality.

The transformative potential of literature can be clearly illustrated through Laurent Gounelle’s novel “*The God Always Travels Incognito*”⁴, which focuses on personal boundaries, self-respect, and psychological growth.

While I read that book, I strongly resonated with Alan, the people pleaser, who always ignored his own feelings and boundaries to meet others expectations, who thought being kind is

⁴ Gounelle, L. (2019). *The God always travels incognito* (O. Egorova, Trans.). Azbuka.

always saying ‘yes’ even when he do not want to or even when it harms him. His story made me realize, that disrespect happens only when we allow it, people do not disrespect you, unless you let them. We unconsciously giving them permission to be rude, mean and arrogant to us, just as Alan did. This book had been one of the game-changer ones on my short list of such literature. This book effectively named the emotions within me that I didn’t know how to call, and explained the things about my own personality way better than I could ever do. Through being a witness of Alan’s mistakes, doubts and consistent growth, I tried to alter myself too, using the same techniques that Alan used. There was a psychologist – Dubre, who had guided Alan through everything, he was the main advisor of Alan, so I used his advises too. Of course, some strategies were challenging at first and others were not common in our culture, so I had to shape them a bit to be suitable for trying. And they actually brought results I never thought they would. While being in this process I learned something, that being nice is not the same as being kind. Being nice is sacrificing yourself for pleasing users, avoiding conflicts and ‘pretending’ to be someone you are not. Kindness, however, is about respecting and valuing everyone, while still treating yourself with care and respect. People do not appreciate people-pleasers anyway, they see them as naïve, predictable and easy to use, that is also something I learned from literature. Accepting the truth wasn’t as easy as it seems but that is the power of literature, it teaches you in most beautiful way possible, unlike the people who might mock you, scold you or even undermine you, literature teaches with an unimaginable gentleness.

What I also get to understand that having boundaries is not selfish or rude as our culture claims. Setting limits does not magically make someone cold, ignorant and disrespectful. Literature teaches all these lesson by showing them on practice, not by lectures, but by mirroring the people who are too relatable for us, so that feels like the book is about us. Watching how Alan overcame his fears, redefined his boundaries, and how he rebuilt his identity, pushed me to do the same. And all of these things made me realize just how all of them are important for self-love, self-respect and for being a bit happier than yesterday.

Conclusion. This is exactly how literature assists adults, teenagers and even younger generation to form their identity, to get the idea of what or who they want to become. Literature teaches people to emotional intelligence, how to handle rage, jealousy, anxiety, fear and even the insecurity itself. Most are ashamed to admit their struggles and ask for help from people around them, but literature is always there for us, not judging but only teaching. It is a safe companion who shows the different shades of the world and people in it. Ultimately, literature guides people through different stories that will teach the lessons they might have never been able to learn, it guides reader to the real changes, to the glow up versions, who are self-understanding, confident and brave enough to take action to become what they want and can become.

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